

GENDER ANALYSIS OF EMPATHETIC SPEECH

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Abstract: This research explores the gender-specific characteristics of empathetic speech. It analyzes differences between men and women in terms of the structure of empathetic utterances, the extent of linguistic unit usage, and the ways emotions are expressed.

Keywords: empathy, empathetic speech, language, speech, linguistic unit, gender analysis, structure, emotional expressiveness, etc.

In our rapidly developing country, as in other fields, significant advancements are being made in the field of linguistics. Social, political, economic, and cultural changes in society are often first reflected in language. Therefore, monitoring the literary language and striving for its purity and cultural refinement remains a pressing issue. Language is a social phenomenon, whereas speech is a linguistic unit created by an individual to convey information or express emotions.

Speech is the process of using the unique and powerful tool called language to perform essential functions. It represents the interaction of linguistic units with phenomena such as reality, thought, consciousness, and context. Speech is the language in motion, formed during the activity of speech organs and composed of word forms, phrases, and sentences. The concept of speech culture and the aspiration for refined speaking have long existed in all languages and are associated with certain linguistic norms as well as ethical and aesthetic expectations. Based on these ethical and aesthetic requirements, various types of speech can be distinguished, one of which is empathetic speech.

Empathetic speech is widely used in situations involving sadness or distress, such as lifting someone's spirits, offering comfort, expressing care, or giving condolences. In modern times, the most common form of empathetic speech can be seen during mourning ceremonies or when comforting someone facing severe illness or life hardships. Like other types of speech and linguistic elements, this emotionally charged form of speech also varies by gender. The degree of directness, the use of specific linguistic units—especially idioms, proverbs, interjections—and emotional engagement differ significantly between men and women.

Women are generally more emotionally expressive and open in their speech compared to men:

"Oh, neighbor, these days must be hard on you. What can we do now? Since yesterday, I've been in anguish thinking about you; I couldn't sleep all night. I feel your pain deeply."

(Shu kunlar ham boshingizda bor ekan-da, qo'shni. Nimayam qilamiz endi! Kechadan beri sizni o'ylab yurak-bag'rim qon bo'ldi, kechasi bilan uxlay olmasdan chiqdim, o'rgilay. Dardingizga sherikman.)

This example demonstrates the high level of expressiveness typical of female speech.

In contrast, male empathetic speech is characterized by brevity, clarity, and a more rational approach:

"It's not about whether you can do it—tell yourself you can. Doubt will break you mentally. Pull yourself together."

"What motivation can I offer? First, do it for your daughter. Pray to God for her bright future. Perform your prayers.

(Qilsammikan emas, qila olaman deng. Ikkilanish sizni ruhan sindiradi. O'zingizni qo'lga oling¹.)

Qanday motivatsiya bera olasiz? – Birinchi o'rinda qizingiz uchun o'zingizni qo'lga oling. Allohdan qizingizning taqdiri go'zal bo'lishini so'rang. Ibodat qiling².)

Women's empathetic speech often includes interjections and complex compound sentences:

"Oh dear! What have you done to yourself? You're completely worn out!"

"My mother stared blankly, glancing at me and then at Grandpa Hoji."

"You've lost your leg! – said Grandpa Hoji, shaking his head. – How did you even get here in this condition?"

(Voy poshsa-a-a! Nima qilib qo'ydingiz, tamom bo'libsiz-ku!

Oyim talmovsiranib, goh menga, goh Hoji buviga qarar edi.

Oyog'ingizdan ayrilibsiz-ku!– dedi Hoji buvi boshini chayqab. –Shu ahvolda qandoq keldingiz?³)

Men, on the other hand, tend to use simpler sentence structures and are less inclined to use interjections. Their empathetic speech also includes logical advice, practical conclusions, and solutions:

"Crying won't help, Qobilboy. Now you need to be stronger and focus your thoughts. You're the head of the family after your father."

¹ <https://darakchi.uz/oz/34114/>

² <https://uzschoolcorpara.uz/uz/Search/Details/5684605>

³ Hoshimov O'. Dunyoning ishlari. – Toshkent, 2019. – B.93.

"Everything will be fine, my friend. Just concentrate on your studies and keep improving yourself. Soon, jobs will be chasing you instead of the other way around."

(Yig'i-sig'idan foyda yo'q, Qobilboy. Endi buyog'iga og'irroq bo'lib, xayolingizni bir joyga qo'yib ish qiling. Otangizdan keyin oilani siz boshqarasiz, axir.

Hali hammasi yaxshi bo'ladi, do'stim. Endi faqat o'qishing kerak, o'z ustingda ishlashing shart. Shunda sen ishni emas, ish seni qidirib keladi.)

Women become active participants in the communication process, analyzing the situation by relating it to personal experiences. Men, in contrast, tend to be passive participants, offering opinions based on facts. Additionally, the use of non-verbal communication also differs between genders. Women actively employ all types of non-verbal elements in empathetic speech. For example, during mourning ceremonies, women express empathy through various forms of weeping, hugging, moaning, remaining silent, and making expressive sounds—enhancing the emotional impact of their speech. These gestures also reflect a high level of empathy towards the deceased's family.

"On the road, she hugged her husband's waist and cried. He hid his face on her shoulder and sobbed quietly. Qoplon understood and slowed the horse."

"At Parpi's funeral, women hugged each other and wailed. Only his youngest daughter Malika stood silently in a corner, shocked

(Yo'lda eri belidan quchib yig'ladi. Eri yelkasiga yuzlarini bosib yig'ladi. Piq-piq yig'ladi! Qoplon nima gapligini fahmladi. Otini ohistaladi⁴Parpi otaning ta'ziasiga kelgan ayollar bir-birining yelkasidan quchib dod-faryod qilishar edi. Faqat kichik qizi Malikagina bir chetda hayron sukut saqlardi.

Men, as in other speech forms, rarely use non-verbal means in empathetic speech, with silence being the most common gesture

Conclusion:

From a gender-based analysis of empathetic speech, it can be concluded that women express their emotions more openly, use complex sentence structures and interjections more frequently, and act as active participants in shaping the speech process. Men, on the other hand, use simpler language, limit their use of idioms and set expressions, and maintain a more restrained, realistic, and concise style. Women's nature—being more emotional, quick to respond, and expressive—is also reflected in their empathetic speech. In

contrast, men's calmness, limited gestures, and tendency to hide emotions are evident in their brief, factual empathetic speech

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